

ANALYSIS AND ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH PSORIASIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14660062>

Abstract: The task set before us for writing this article was Analysis and assessment of the quality of life of patients with acne. To achieve our goals and objectives, we analyzed the study of the quality of life of patients with acne through observation using a questionnaire using the Dermatological Life Quality Index (DLQI) and the APSEA scale. As a result, we came to the conclusion that damage to the facial skin due to acne causes a psychotraumatic state, which is maximally aggravated by interpersonal and socio-psychological relationships, which contribute to a decrease in the quality of life in these patients. Such patients may develop: social phobia, depression, anxiety neurosis. In turn, the degree of negative impact of acne on the quality of life is not comparable with the objective condition of patients: even mild acne can contribute to an increased risk of developing mental illnesses and become one of the causes of suicide in 10-24 year olds.

Key words: Treatment, acne, Dermatological Life Quality Index, APSEA, analysis, patients, assessment.

АНАЛИЗ И ОЦЕНКА КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ПСОРИАЗОМ

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Аннотация: Задачей, поставленной перед нами при написании данной статьи, был анализ и оценка качества жизни пациентов с акне. Для достижения поставленных целей и задач мы провели исследование качества жизни пациентов с акне через наблюдение с использованием анкеты, основанной на Индексе качества жизни в дерматологии (DLQI) и шкале APSEA.

В результате исследования мы пришли к выводу, что повреждение кожи лица из-за акне вызывает психотравматическое состояние, которое максимально усугубляется межличностными и социально-психологическими отношениями, что способствует снижению качества жизни у этих пациентов. У таких пациентов могут развиваться: социальная фобия, депрессия, тревожный невроз. В свою очередь, степень негативного воздействия акне на качество жизни несопоставима с объективным состоянием пациентов: даже лёгкие формы акне могут способствовать повышенному риску развития психических заболеваний и стать одной из причин самоубийств среди людей в возрасте 10-24 лет.

Ключевые слова: Лечение, акне, индекс качества жизни дерматологических заболеваний, APSEA, анализ, пациенты, оценка.

INTRODUCTION

Acne vulgaris is one of the most common diseases in dermatology, affecting up to 85% of adolescents and 10% of adults. The peak incidence occurs during puberty, the most “fragile” age, when the formation of a person as an individual occurs, affecting all areas of his life. Most adolescents with facial acne complain of preoccupation with social interactions, especially when

contacting new people and the opposite sex, increased irritability, and a feeling of inferiority, which can later lead to depression, social maladaptation and self-doubt. This dermatosis is a chronic inflammatory disease of the pilosebaceous structures, manifested by various eruptive elements in the face, back, and upper chest. Depending on the severity, the following forms are distinguished: comedonal, papulopustular, conglobate acne. Severe clinical forms often lead to the formation of disfiguring scars that negatively affect a person's self-esteem. However, regardless of the severity, all rashes are a psychological burden for a person, which is accompanied by stress, depression, anxiety and, as a result, a decrease in quality of life. A special feature of acne as a dermatosis is that it affects exposed parts of the body, and most importantly, the person's face, which is one of the main tools of relationships. Consequently, this disease significantly affects the psycho-emotional state of patients and their interaction with the outside world.

Purpose of the study. Analysis and assessment of the quality of life of patients with acne

Materials and methods of research. The study of the quality of life of patients with acne was carried out during observation using a questionnaire using the Dermatological Life Quality Index (DLQI) and the APSEA scale. 25 patients (19-23 years old) were interviewed, 14 women, 11 men. Questionnaire on the psychological and social effects of acne - APSEA (Assessment of Psychological and Social Effects of Acne) contains 15 questions. The first 6 questions have 4 answer options, you need to choose only one of the four for each. The answer is awarded 0, 3, 6 or 9 points. The remaining 9 questions are scored on a visual analog scale from 0 to 10 points. The maximum number of points for the test is 144, the minimum is 0. The higher the score, the more acne disrupts the patient's quality of life. The DLQI consists of 6 main dimensions: symptoms and well-being, daily activities, leisure, work and study, personal relationships and treatment. The maximum score is 30, and the quality of life of patients is inversely proportional to the number of points.

Results of the study and their discussions. In the observed patients, the average APSEA score was 67.6 ± 26.7 . High index values were achieved due to indicators associated with dissatisfaction with one's own appearance and a feeling of awkwardness, psychological difficulties of being in public places, which is comparable to the quality of life of patients with asthma, epilepsy, diabetes, arthritis, and coronary insufficiency. The average value of the DLQI index: 8.75 ± 4.71 , this indicates that the disease has a moderate impact on the patient's life.

Conclusions. Thus, damage to the facial skin due to acne causes a psychotraumatic state, which is maximally aggravated by interpersonal and socio-psychological relationships, which contribute to a decrease in the quality of life in these patients. Such patients may develop: social phobia, depression, anxiety neurosis. In turn, the degree of negative impact of acne on the quality of life is not comparable with the objective condition of patients: even mild acne can contribute to an increased risk of developing mental illnesses and become one of the causes of suicide in 10-24 year olds. Therefore, it is important that healthcare providers treating patients with acne are aware of emerging symptoms of depression to help initiate early mental health interventions when needed.

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